

1 Increasing catechin and procyanidin accumulation by high CO₂ treatments in *Fragaria*
2 *vesca*.
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24 **ABSTRACT**

25 This paper deals with the impact of low temperature and high CO₂ levels on flavonols,
26 proanthocyanidins and anthocyanins, synthesized via branched pathways from common
27 precursors, in strawberries (*Fragaria vesca* L.). Simultaneously extracted flavonoids
28 from untreated (air) and CO₂-treated (20% or 40%) strawberries were identified with Q-
29 TOF equipment and quantified by HPLC-quadrupole. We found that flavan 3-ols
30 accumulated only in CO₂ treated strawberries, whereas in untreated fruit, flavonoid
31 production was redirected towards anthocyanin accumulation with a sharp decrease in
32 catechin and procyanidin B3 levels. Catechin induction could be associated with the
33 potential of high CO₂ treatments to reduce the incidence and severity of decay due to its
34 antifungal activity. Although flavan 3-ols were induced by high CO₂ treatments,
35 differences were observed when comparing 20% and 40% CO₂ treated fruit. The
36 accumulation of flavan-3 ols in 20% CO₂ treated fruit was concomitant with an increase
37 in flavonol content (quercetin and kaempferol derivatives). By contrast, ascorbic acid
38 levels increased in 40% CO₂-treated fruit. In spite of the variations in the accumulation
39 of flavonoids, a similar antioxidant capacity was found in untreated and CO₂-treated
40 Mara de Bois strawberries.

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42 **KEYWORDS:** flavonoids, proanthocyanidins, strawberries, high CO₂, ascorbic acid,
43 mass spectroscopy, antioxidant activity.

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46 INTRODUCTION

47 Strawberry (*Fragaria vesca* L.) is a high-value fruit due to its pleasing taste and flavour.
48 However, there are extensive postharvest losses produced mainly by fungal attack, rapid
49 water loss and structure deterioration. For this reason, there is a growing interest in the
50 development of technologies for controlling fungal decay while maintaining fruit quality. The
51 fungistatic effects of high CO₂ levels on strawberries are well known¹. We previously
52 reported that the effectiveness of high CO₂ treatment for controlling fungal decay in table
53 grapes, another high CO₂ tolerant fruit, was not mediated by the induction of specific
54 phenylpropanoid genes (Phenylalanine ammonia lyase, PAL; Chalcone synthase, CHS;
55 Stilbene synthase, STS)². Additionally, short-term exposure to high CO₂ levels had no
56 significant effect on anthocyanin content, while fruit stored in air at 0 °C had the highest
57 anthocyanin levels. Anthocyanin induction at low temperature was also reported in different
58 strawberry cultivars, as well as in other plant systems^{3, 4}. As anthocyanins are synthesized via
59 branched biosynthesis pathways with proanthocyanidins, our aim in the present work was to
60 analyse the feasibility of high CO₂ levels for channeling phenolic compound precursors into
61 proanthocyanidins instead of anthocyanins. Furthermore, since proanthocyanidins, and mainly
62 catechins⁶, have been linked with protection against pathogens⁵ the development of
63 technologies that enhance its production is desirable. Proanthocyanidins are polymeric
64 flavonoid compounds composed of flavan-3-ol subunits. They influence the sensory
65 properties of astringency. Nevertheless, several components, other than phenolics, are known
66 to influence the perception of astringency, including ethanol, acidity, pH and polysaccharides
67 among others. Although proanthocyanidin concentrations have been estimated in several plant
68 sources using simple colorimetric methods, proanthocyanidins have also been reported in
69 different foods by employing more sensitive, specific methods such as HPLC and Mass
70 Spectrometry⁷. The building blocks or starter units of most proanthocyanidins are the flavan-

71 3-ols (+)-catechins and (-)-epicatechins, whose last common biosynthetic intermediate is
72 leucoanthocyanidin, an intermediate in anthocyanin biosynthesis, also referred to as flavan
73 3,4-diol, connected with the flavonol precursor molecules⁸. Consequently, differences in
74 proanthocyanidin levels due to the effect of high CO₂ levels and low temperature should be
75 considered together with the changes in anthocyanins concentrations and also with flavonols.
76 Additionally, flavonols and their glycosides appear to be mainly involved in response
77 mechanisms against abiotic stress⁹ and may contribute to environmental stress tolerance¹⁰.
78 Furthermore, all these flavonoids act as agents against reactive oxygen species (ROS)
79 generated during the normal ripening stage and by stressful storage conditions that cause
80 oxidative damage in the fruit. Ascorbic acid also has the property of scavenging oxidants and
81 free radicals, and strawberry fruit is one of the richest sources of ascorbic acid among fruits¹¹.
82 In the present work variations in ascorbic acid and antioxidant activity levels were analysed in
83 untreated and CO₂-treated fruit. Ascorbic acid levels were quantified by high-performance
84 anion-exchange chromatography (HPAEC) and antioxidant capacity was determined by
85 means of photochemiluminescence (PCL). In the PCL assay the photochemical generation of
86 free radicals was combined with sensitive chemiluminescence detection¹⁴. This method is
87 suitable for measuring the scavenging capacity of antioxidants present in water-soluble
88 fractions in pulp fruit extracts against the radical anion superoxide.

89 The objectives of this study were to identify and quantify simultaneously anthocyanidins,
90 flavonols, proanthocyanidins and their flavan-3-ols monomers in freshly harvested
91 strawberries, using Q-TOF equipment and quantification by HPLC-quadrupole. Second, to
92 analyse the effect of low temperature and high CO₂ treatments on the accumulation of
93 anthocyanidins, proanthocyanidins and flavonols. Third, to study the relationship between
94 variations in flavonoid levels including ascorbic acid and the antioxidant capacity of untreated
95 and CO₂-treated fruit. All the aforementioned information is essential to evaluate a beneficial

96 high CO₂ treatment able to maintain initial antioxidant capacity and avoid damage caused by
97 fungal attack.

98 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

99 **Plant material**

100 Organic strawberries (*Fragaria vesca* L. cv. Mara de Bois) were harvested by hand in
101 May 2010 at the first flowering in an orchard in San Sebastian de los Reyes (Madrid,
102 Spain). Fruit were harvested at the same mature stage when fruit have reached full size
103 (9.8% total soluble solids, 0.8% titratable acidity as citric acid and colour parameters L*
104 18, a* 40, b*29). After harvest, fruit were transported to Institute of Food Science
105 Technology and Nutrition within 2 h. Fruit selected for uniform size and colour were
106 stored at 0 °C (± 0.5) and >95% relative humidity in three sealed containers with a
107 capacity of 1 m³. Fifteen plastic boxes containing approximately 0.5 kg of strawberries
108 per box were stored in each container for 3 days and exposed to a continuous flow of air
109 (untreated fruit) or a gas mixture containing 20% or 40% CO₂. The same O₂
110 concentration (20%) was maintained in all three lots. CO₂ and O₂ concentrations were
111 measured using a gas analyzer PBI Dansensor mod. Checkmate 9900. Initially and at
112 the end of the 3-day sampling period, 45 strawberries were taken for quality analysis,
113 and another 45 were removed at random from each of the treatment groups and divided
114 into three batches of 15 berries. The 15 strawberries from each batch, used as a
115 biological replicate, were mixed, frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80 °C for
116 further analysis. From each of the three biological replicates, at least two different
117 measurements were taken.

118 **Identification of flavonoid composition by MS and-MS²**

119 For the extraction of water-soluble flavonoids, fruit samples (3 g) were homogenized in
120 10 mL of ultra-pure water, sonicated for 10 min and centrifuged at 30,000 x g for 20
121 min, and the supernatants were then filtered through a membrane of 0.45 µm pore size.
122 A preliminary identification of the compounds to be studied was made by the
123 Quadrupole Time-of-Flight (Q-TOF) mass spectrometer as described in this section.
124 Then, under the same chromatographic conditions we proceeded to quantify these
125 compounds in SIM (Selected Ion Monitoring) mode by HPLC-Quadrupole. Analyses
126 were performed using an Agilent 1200 series LC, comprised of a quaternary pump
127 G1311A with an integrated degasser G1322A, thermostated autosampler G1330B,
128 thermostated column compartment G1316A, coupled with an Agilent 6530 Accurate-
129 Mass Quadrupole Time-of-Flight (Q-TOF) LC/MS with ESI-Jet Stream Technology
130 (Agilent Technologies, Waldbronn, Germany). A 10 µL sample was separated in a
131 Kromasil C18 column 5µm 4.6x150mm (Análisis Vínicos, S. L, Madrid) eluted with a
132 mobile phase made up of a mixture of deionized water (solvent A) and acetonitrile
133 (solvent B) both containing 0.1% formic acid, at a flow rate of 0.8 mL/min. The solvent
134 gradient changed according to the following conditions: from 90% A to 70% A in 30
135 min, to 65% A in 5 min, to 55% A in 5 min and then back to the initial conditions in 10
136 min. MS and MS² experiments were performed to identify and characterize flavonoids.
137 The Q-TOF acquisition method was High Resolution 4GHz, mass range low 1700 m/z.
138 Ionization was achieved by Atmospheric Pressure Electrospray Ionization (ESI) with a
139 drying gas flow rate of 10 L/min at 350 °C, sheath gas flow 7.5 L/min at 325 °C,
140 nebulizer 35 psi, cap voltage 3500V, nozzle voltage 1000V, fragmentor voltage 150V
141 and skimmer voltage 65V. The experiments were done with both negative polarity (for
142 flavonols and flavanols) with reference masses (119.0363 and 966.0007 m/z) and
143 positive polarity (for anthocyanins) with reference masses (121.0508 and 922.0097 m/z)

144 to obtain the most sensitivity. For auto MS² experiments constant collision energy of
145 20eV was employed. The Data Acquisition (version B.04.01) and Qualitative Analysis
146 (version B.04.00) of MassHunter Workstation Software were used (Agilent
147 Technologies, Waldbroon, Germany).

148 **Quantification of flavonoid composition by MS.**

149 Analyses were carried out using an Agilent 1100 series LC, comprised of a quaternary
150 pump G1311A with an integrated degasser G1322A, autosampler G1313A,
151 thermostated column compartment G1316A, coupled with an Agilent G1946D
152 Quadrupole mass spectrometer (Agilent Technologies, Waldbroon, Germany). Sample
153 separation was done in the same way as that for those samples explained in previous
154 paragraphs. 20 µL or 5 µL samples were injected for the analysis of the compounds
155 quantified in negative or positive polarity respectively. Ionization was by ESI source,
156 with the electrospray capillary voltage set to 4000 V, fragmentor 150V, a nebulizing gas
157 flow rate 12 L/h at 45 psig, and a drying temperature of 350 °C. Data acquisition and
158 analysis were carried out with Agilent ChemStation B.04.01 SP1 Software. Strawberry
159 polyphenols were quantified using data acquired in the SIM mode. For negative polarity
160 m/z 273 (afzelechin), 289 (catechin), 461 (kaempferol glucuronide), 477 (quercetin 3-
161 glucuronide), 489 (kaempferol acetylglucoside), 577 (procyanidin B1 and B3) were
162 used. For positive polarity m/z 433 (pelargonidin 3-glucoside), 475 (pelargonidin 3-
163 acetylglucoside), 519 (pelargonidin 3-malonylglucoside), 535 (cyanidin
164 malonylglucoside), 579 (pelargonidin 3-rutinoside) were employed. These compounds
165 were quantified from the areas of their chromatographic peaks in SIM mode by
166 comparison with calibration curves obtained with external standards. (+)-Catechin,
167 pelargonidin chloride and procyanidin B1 were purchased from Extrasynthese (Genay,
168 France). These standards are specific for HPLC assay and the purity of them is ≥ 95%.

169 Individual polyphenol levels were expressed as μg catechin/g fresh weight (FW) for all
170 the compounds analysed by negative polarity and as μg pelargonidin/g FW for all the
171 compounds analysed by positive polarity. From each of the three replicates two
172 different measurements were taken.

173 **Extraction and chromatographic determination of ascorbic acid.**

174 To determine ascorbic acid concentration, 3 g of frozen fruit sample was homogenized
175 in 10 mL of ultra-pure water, centrifuged at 30,000 x g for 20 min, and the supernatants
176 were then filtered through a membrane of 0.45 μm pore size as described Blanch et al.,
177 (2012). The ascorbic acid content of untreated and CO_2 -treated fruit was analysed by
178 HPAEC using a Metrohm Advanced Compac ion chromatography instrument (867 IC.
179 Metrohm) equipped with a Metrosep Organic Acids column (7.8 x 250 mm), an IC-819
180 conductivity detector, an IC Pump 818 and a coupled IC-837 degasser. Samples were
181 eluted from the column with an isocratic gradient of 0.5 mM HClO_4 with 50 mM LiCl
182 suppression over 20 min at a flow rate of 0.5 mL/min. Data was acquired with ICNet
183 2.3 Metrohm software. Ascorbate acid was identified by its retention time and
184 quantified on the basis of the calibration curve derived from standard (+)-sodium L.
185 ascorbate (Sigma, Steinheim, Germany). The content was expressed as mg/g FW of the
186 sample. From each of the three replicates two different measurements were taken.

187 **Antioxidant capacity**

188 The scavenging capacity of the water-soluble fraction of untreated and CO_2 -treated fruit was
189 determined using a photochemiluminescence (PCL) assay. In the PCL assay the
190 photochemical generation of free radicals is combined with sensitive detection by using
191 chemiluminescence. This reaction is induced by optical excitation of a photosensitizer S
192 which results in the generation of the superoxide radical O_2^{15} . The free radicals are visualised

193 with the chemiluminescent detection reagent luminol. This reaction takes place in the
194 Photochem[®]. The hydrophilic antioxidants were measured with an antioxidant capacity of
195 water-soluble substance (ACW) kit (Analytik jenaAG). 1.5 mL reagent 1 (buffer solution pH
196 10.5), 1 mL reagent 2 (water), 25 μ L reagent 3 (photosensitizer) and 2-30 μ L antioxidant
197 solution (reagent 4, ascorbic acid) were mixed and measured. 15 μ L of sample were used to
198 determine antioxidant capacity. The results were expressed as μ g ascorbic acid equivalents/
199 mg FW of the sample.

200 **Statistical analysis**

201 One-way ANOVA and correlational analyses were performed using SPSS ver. 19.0.
202 The multicomparison of means was assessed by the Bonferroni's test at 0.05
203 significance level. The main effects of CO₂ treatment, storage time, and treatment time
204 interaction on strawberry fruit were analysed.

205 **RESULTS**

206 **Identification of *Fragaria vesca* flavonoids**

207 Flavonoid identification was performed by employing exact mass and fragmentation
208 characteristics provided by Q-TOF using positive and negative modes according to
209 analytes. The following peak data obtained in the Q-TOF analysis are summarized in
210 Table 1 including the exact mass molecular ion, the tentative molecular formula, the
211 score (%), the main fragments observed in MS² and the identified flavonoid
212 compounds. Respect to the results obtained for anthocyanins from positive mode MS²,
213 four peaks with MS² fragmentation ions at m/z 271 were identified as derivatives of
214 pelargonidin. Peak 1 with [M⁺] at m/z 433 and a subsequent loss of 162 amu (hexose)
215 was pelargonidin-3-glucoside, the major anthocyanin in strawberries. Peak 2 with [M⁺]
216 at m/z 579 and a loss of 308 amu (deoxyhexose-hexose) upon fragmentation was

217 assigned as pelargonidin 3-rutinoside. Less polar pelargonidin glycosides, peaks 4 and
218 5, had $[M^+]$ at m/z 519 and 475, respectively (Table 1). During fragmentation peak 4
219 lost 248 amu which most likely represented the residue composed of hexose and
220 malonic acid, (malonylglucoside) and was identified as pelargonidin 3-malonyl-
221 glucoside. Peak 5 lost 204 amu (acetylglucoside) during fragmentation and was
222 identified as pelargonidin-3-acetyl-glucoside. Peaks 3 and 6, both with $[M^+]$ at m/z 535
223 and a subsequent loss of 248 amu suggested the presence of cyanidin-malonyl-
224 glucoside isomers. This fragmentation behaviour is in accordance with literature data
225 for cyanidin 3-(3''-malonyl) glucoside^{16,17}. The more stable cyanidin 3-(3''-malonyl)
226 glucoside only yielded a product ion at m/z 287, not at 3-(6''-malonyl glucoside),
227 showing that the acyl linkage to the 3''-position of the sugar was more stable than the
228 corresponding linkage to the 6''-position. We further observed the absence of
229 anthocyanins derived from leucodelphinidin.

230 Table 1 also gives the results for flavanols from negative mode MS². Flavan-3-ols and
231 dimeric proanthocyanidins polyphenols were identified and have been included in
232 Table 1 as follows: (+)-catechin peak 9, afzelechin peak 10, and two B types
233 proanthocyanidin dimers peaks 7 and peak 8. Peak 7 had $[M-H]$ at m/z 577 and was
234 identified as B1 (EC-4, 8-C) after comparison with the authentic standard. Peak 8 with
235 $[M-H]$ at m/z 577 probably contained B3 (C-4, 8-C), the most abundant flavanol after
236 (+)-catechin in strawberries, with a fragmentation pattern in negative mode consistent
237 with that of a flavanol²⁰. Peak 9 which had $[M-H]$ at m/z 289 was identified as (+)-
238 catechin. Peak 10 with $[M-H]$ at m/z 273 was identified as afzelechin with a
239 fragmentation pattern in negative mode in accordance with that of a flavanol²¹. Table 1
240 also gives the results for flavonols from negative mode MS². Peak 11 with $[M-H]$ at m/z
241 477 and the elimination of a glucurone unit (176 amu) during fragmentation was

242 identified as quercetin 3-glucuronide (Figure 1A), previously reported to be the major
243 flavonol in strawberries^{18,19}. Two peaks (12 and 13) were identified as kaempferol
244 derivatives due to MS² fragmentation ions at m/z 285 in negative mode MS. Peak 12,
245 identified as kaempferol 3-glucuronide, with mass 461 lost a glucurone unit (176 amu)
246 during fragmentation, and peak 13 with mass 489, which lost a 204 amu
247 (acetylglucoside) was identified as kaempferol 3-acetylglucoside^{19,20} (Table 1).

248 Figure 1 shows the Extracted Ion Chromatogram (EIC) from HPLC-ESI-MS analysis
249 corresponding to flavonoids compounds quantified in positive polarity (peaks 1 to 6)
250 Figure 1A or negative polarity (peaks 7 to 13) Figure 1B. Insert A₁ represents the
251 fragmentation pattern of pelargonidin 3-*O*-glucoside (peak 1), the most abundant
252 anthocyanin in *Fragaria vesca* cv. Mara de Bois. Insert B₂ represents the fragmentation
253 pattern of (+)-catechin (peak 9) one of the most important flavanols in strawberry.

254 Figure 2 represents the Extracted Ion Chromatogram (EIC) from HPLC-ESI-MS
255 analysis corresponding to dimeric proanthocyanidins polyphenols (procyanidins B1 and
256 B3) and other two suggested dimmers of procyanidin. Inserts shows fragmentation
257 pattern in negative mode from procyanidin B1 (peak 7) (EC-4, 8C) after comparison
258 with the authentic standard (insert A) and peak 8 probably contained B3 (C-4, 8-C) one
259 of the most abundant flavanol in *Fragaria vesca* (insert B).

260 **Changes in the levels of anthocyanidin-specific branch products of the flavonoid** 261 **pathway.**

262 The anthocyanins in *Fragaria vesca* cv. Mara de Bois were pelargonidin and cyanidin
263 glycosides. Delphinidin derivatives were not detected. Pelargonidin-based anthocyanin
264 content in was much higher than that of cyanidin-based anthocyanins (Table 2). The
265 main anthocyanin, pelargonidin 3-glucoside in freshly harvested fruit was $842.09 \pm$

266 46.41 µg/g FW, while that of cyanidin 3-malonylglucoside, the main cyanidin-based
267 anthocyanin was $9.80 \pm 1.1.5$ µg/g FW. The same anthocyanidin profile was identified
268 in fruit with and without CO₂ treatment. The results indicated that all the different
269 anthocyanins detected in freshly harvested fruit increased significantly in untreated fruit
270 stored in air, except for pelargonidin 3-acetyl-glucoside which only increased in 40%
271 CO₂-treated fruit (Table 2).

272 **Changes in the levels of flavonol-specific branch products of the flavonoid**
273 **pathway.**

274 The flavonol profile in *Fragaria vesca* cv. Mara de Bois consisted of quercetin
275 derivatives, mainly quercetin 3-glucuronide with values of 39.14 ± 2.44 µg/g FW,
276 followed by minor amounts of other kaempferol derivatives such as kaempferol 3-
277 glucuronide and kaempferol 3-acetyl-glucoside (Table 3). The quercetin 3-glucuronide
278 content increased in both untreated and 20% CO₂ treated fruit, whereas in the case of
279 40% CO₂ treated fruit the values exhibited were similar to those found in freshly
280 harvested fruit. Kaempferol 3-glucuronide content also increased in untreated and 20%
281 CO₂-treated fruit unlike that in 40% CO₂-treated fruit (Table 3). The myricetin
282 derivatives were not detected.

283 **Changes in the levels of proanthocyanidin-specific branch products of the**
284 **flavonoid pathway.**

285 The levels of catechin in freshly harvested strawberries were 10.33 ± 3.00 µg/g FW.
286 The content of catechin increased after 3 days of 20% CO₂ treatment and reached levels
287 1.54 times higher than those found in freshly harvested fruit (Figure 3). In contrast,
288 storage at 0 °C in air caused a marked decrease in catechin content reaching values that
289 were only 8% of those found in CO₂-treated fruit. Additionally, 40% CO₂-treated fruit

290 had enhanced catechin levels compared with freshly harvested strawberries, reaching
291 values of $14.14 \pm 0.97 \mu\text{g/g FW}$ (Figure 3). Epicatechin was not detected and the levels
292 of afzelechin did not change.

293 Procyanidin B3 was the predominant proanthocyanidin with an initial value of $10.05 \pm$
294 $1.95 \mu\text{g/g FW}$. However, procyanidin B3 content was found to decrease markedly to
295 28% of its initial value during storage at low temperature for 3 days in air. (Figure 4). A
296 slight decrease in procyanidin B1 content was also found in untreated fruit. The
297 opposite was observed in the case of high CO_2 treated fruit (in both 20% and 40%),
298 where there was a sharp increase in procyanidin B3, reaching values at least 4 times
299 higher than those found in untreated fruit. Procyanidin B1 levels also significantly
300 increased in 20% CO_2 -treated fruit reaching values of $7.08 \pm 0.61 \mu\text{g/g FW}$ (Figure 4).

301 **Antioxidant capacity and changes in ascorbic acid and total flavonoids.**

302 The antioxidant capacity of untreated and CO_2 -treated fruit, as indicated by μg of
303 ascorbic acid/mg FW, is shown in Table 4. In this table, the amount of ascorbic acid
304 (mg/g FW) and the calculated sum of total flavonoids (mg/g FW), including the
305 identified and quantified flavonols, flavanols and anthocyanins, is also shown. Our
306 results indicate that the total sum of flavonoids is quite similar in untreated and CO_2 -
307 treated fruit, as well as in freshly harvested strawberries. In the case of CO_2 -treated
308 fruit, although an accumulation in flavan-3-ols and dimmers was detected in both 20
309 and 40% CO_2 -treated fruit, there were differences with regard to ascorbic acid,
310 anthocyanins and flavonols dependent on CO_2 levels. The highest amount of ascorbic
311 acid content was detected in fruit treated with 40% CO_2 for 3 days (Table 4) whereas in
312 20% CO_2 -treated fruit the ascorbic acid levels were similar to those found in freshly
313 harvested fruit. Furthermore, in strawberries treated with 20% CO_2 , the total

314 anthocyanins and of flavonols increased significantly, whereas in those exposed to 40%
315 CO₂ no differences were observed when compared with those at time of harvesting. In
316 spite of these differences, similar antioxidant capacities were detected in both 20% and
317 40% CO₂-treated fruit, as well as in untreated fruit, and the only significant increase was
318 observed in untreated fruit compared with freshly harvested fruit.

319

320 **DISCUSSION**

321 Regulation of anthocyanin and proanthocyanidin production in fruit during storage is of
322 special interest because of the significant role they have as antioxidant, as defence
323 compounds against fungal diseases, and as protection against environmental stress
324 conditions. Advances have been made with regard to factors involved in
325 proanthocyanidin and anthocyanidin gene regulation in different plant systems,
326 including strawberry fruits ^{22,23}. However, flux control and the manner in which low
327 temperature and high CO₂ levels influence anthocyanin production with respect to
328 alterations in proanthocyanidin levels is still incomplete and not well understood.
329 Anthocyanins and proanthocyanins are produced by two related but distinct branches of
330 the flavonoid pathway, so leucoanthocyanidin (flavan 3, 4 diols) can be directly
331 reduced to 2, 3 *trans*-flavan 3-ols, such as (+)-catechins, or converted to 3-OH-
332 anthocyanidin molecules²⁴. Therefore, in the present work we analysed the effect of
333 low temperature and high CO₂ levels in directing the metabolic flux to either
334 anthocyanins or flavan-3-ols. Moreover, since the production of anthocyanidins and
335 proanthocyanidins share didydroflavonols as precursor molecules, we also analysed
336 alterations in the amounts of flavonols.

337 As regards the anthocyanidin profile, in *Fragaria vesca* cv. Mara de Bois strawberries
338 (Table 1 and Table 2), pelargonidin 3-glucoside is the main anthocyanin as in other
339 cultivars and species²⁵, followed by cyanidin 3-glucoside and minor amounts of other
340 pelargonidin derivatives. There are many reports indicating that anthocyanin levels are
341 affected by a variety of chemical and environmental factors²⁶, and specifically, that
342 exposure to low temperatures produces a rapid increase in anthocyanin accumulation
343 ^{3,4-13}. In the present work a significant accumulation of anthocyanins occurred in
344 strawberry fruit stored in air at low temperature, this accumulation was limited in CO₂-
345 treated fruit, and even more highly restricted in 40%-CO₂ treated fruit. Moreover, the
346 increase in anthocyanin levels in untreated fruit stored in air was associated with a
347 sharp decrease in the amount of flavan-3-ols monomers and procyanidin dimers. These
348 data suggest that in untreated fruit there is a redirection of the metabolic flux from
349 leucoanthocyanidins towards anthocyanins. Interestingly, CO₂-treated fruit, mainly
350 those with 20% CO₂, anthocyanin accumulation in pulp tissues of strawberries did not
351 decline, while an increase in the accumulation of procyanidins B1 and B3 was
352 quantified (Table 1, Figure 4). Furthermore, in the case of monomeric subunits the
353 levels of free 2, 3 *trans*-flavan 3-ols also increased significantly in CO₂-treated fruit (20
354 and 40%) (Table 1, Figure 3). Conversely, a pronounced decrease in catechin levels
355 was quantified in untreated fruit stored in air at low temperature. In *Fragaria x annassa*
356 cv. Camarosa epicatechin and catechin were not detectable, even though moderate
357 levels have been reported for other cultivars such as Camp Dover^{27,28}. The fact that
358 catechin and proanthocyanidin levels in CO₂-treated strawberries increased but
359 anthocyanin accumulation did not decline, would seem to indicate an apparent lack of
360 competition between the anthocyanidin and proanthocyanidins branches. The reported
361 inducible accumulation of procyanidins and catechins in high CO₂-treated strawberries,

362 could be one of the factors explaining the resistance to fungal decay. In this sense,
363 flavan-3-ols, such as catechins, epicatechins and oligomeric proanthocyanidins have
364 been shown to have inhibitory and antifungal properties towards different fungi,
365 including *Botrytis cinerea*⁶, and against insects²⁹. Proanthocyanidin accumulation has
366 also been associated with high ambient CO₂ concentrations (70 Pa), suggesting a
367 potential positive effect on proanthocyanidin production as a result of greenhouse gas
368 emission^{30,31}. Additionally, since procyanidins are either metabolized or strongly bound
369 to other components of the plant, we cannot rule out the possibility that the increase in
370 procyanidins could be contributed to the reported beneficial effect of high CO₂
371 treatment on strawberry storage. In line with this, the enhancement of other polymers,
372 fructo-oligosaccharides, in 20% CO₂-treated Mara de Bois strawberries, polymers that
373 showed a high ability to bind water molecules resulted in protective benefits in
374 maintaining water status and cell integrity³².

375 Anthocyanidin and/or proanthocyanidin accumulation did not impair flavonol
376 production of quercetin and kaempferol derivatives in either untreated (air) or 20%
377 CO₂-treated fruit, (Table 1 and Table 3). It is well known that the amounts of flavonols
378 vary substantially among the different strawberry cultivars, although in general,
379 quercetin and kaempferol are the major flavonols and occur as 3-glucosides and 3-*O*-
380 glucuronides^{34,35}. For the most part, quercetin derivative levels were significantly
381 higher than those of kaempferol derivatives²⁸. Flavonols and their glycosides appear to
382 be mainly involved in response mechanisms against abiotic stress⁹. Numerous studies
383 suggest that flavonol glucosides of quercetin and kaempferol have multiple functional
384 roles in plant responses to abiotic stress^{24,36-37}, including water deficit stress in response
385 to UV-B radiation³⁸, and may contribute to ozone tolerance³⁹. We have shown that the
386 magnitude of flavonol accumulation in untreated fruit and 20% CO₂-treated fruit stored

387 at 0 °C was similar but, no increase in kaempferol 3-glucuronide and quercetin 3-
388 glucuronide levels occurred in fruit treated with 40% CO₂. Therefore it was not
389 possible to quantify significant differences with respect to freshly harvested fruit.

390 Apart from the advantages mentioned above, flavonoids also act as antioxidants⁴⁰. Our
391 results indicate (Table 4) that fruit stored in air or with high CO₂ levels exhibited a
392 similar antioxidant capacity, although compared with freshly harvested fruit a
393 significant increase was only observed in untreated fruit stored in air. This indicated
394 that strawberry fruit stored in air at severe low temperature had high scavenging
395 activity for generated active oxygen species. Considering the changes in the specific
396 flavonoids quantified, including that of ascorbic acid, the increase in anthocyanin
397 content seems to be responsible for the increase in antioxidant content in untreated
398 fruit. In this respect, untreated table grapes stored in air at 0 °C had both the highest
399 anthocyanin content and antioxidant capacity, determined by TEAC assay⁴¹. Ascorbic
400 acid levels increased significantly in strawberries treated with 40% CO₂, whereas in
401 untreated fruit and fruit exposed to 20% CO₂ the levels of this metabolite did not differ
402 from those at the time of harvest. Variations in ascorbic acid levels in strawberries in
403 response to temperature storage have already been reported by other authors^{11, 43}. We
404 suggest that the increase in ascorbate levels with too high CO₂ levels (40% CO₂), as
405 opposed to 20% CO₂, could be associated with susceptibility to CO₂ injury. Indeed,
406 increases in levels of ascorbate under stress conditions have been reported⁴⁴. The
407 increase in ascorbic acid in 40% CO₂-treated fruit may result from an activation of its
408 multiple biosynthetic pathways and also through increased ascorbate recycling. Further
409 analyses should be carried out to see if this increase in ascorbic acid was accompanied
410 by changes in the glutathione pool, thus resulting in a substantial change in the
411 intracellular redox state of 40% CO₂-treated tissues. Furthermore, the increase in the

412 content of ascorbic acid in these treated fruits was concomitant with the lowest values
413 registered for total flavonoids, except for catechin and procyanidins that showed a very
414 high antioxidant capacity (data not shown). As no differences in antioxidant capacity
415 were observed between fruit treated with 40% CO₂ and freshly harvested fruit, we
416 reasoned that the antioxidant and radical scavenging activities of ascorbic acid and
417 catechins could be sufficient to prevent modifications in their antioxidant capacity,
418 although the underlying mechanism remains unclear. 20% CO₂ treatment led to an
419 increase in catechin, proanthocyanidin and flavonol glycoside (quercetin 3-glucuronide
420 and kaempferol 3-glucuronide) levels. These flavonols, besides acting as antioxidant
421 agents against ROS⁴⁵, are also involved in the response against abiotic stress and fungal
422 decay⁴⁶. Undoubtedly, given the antibacterial and antifungal activities exhibited by (+)-
423 catechin⁶, its induction by high CO₂ treatments would serve to protect strawberries
424 from fungal attack and makes this procedure an attractive alternative to other chemical
425 treatments. Additionally, CO₂ treatment of fruit is a good system that clearly shows the
426 connection between proanthocyanidins, anthocyanidins and flavonols. Further studies
427 will be necessary to determine the metabolic implications and to identify the
428 mechanisms underlying the redirection of anthocyanidin into flavan-3-ols in CO₂-
429 treated fruit.

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591 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

592 **Figure 1:** Extracted Ion Chromatogram (EIC) from HPLC-ESI-MS analysis
593 corresponding to (A) flavonoids quantified in positive polarity (peaks 1 to 6) from
594 *Fragaria vesca* strawberry. Insert A₁: MS² Scan spectra at *m/z* 433 of pelargonidin 3-*O*-
595 glucuronide (peak 1), collision energy 20eV. (B) Flavonids quantified in negative
596 polarity (peaks 7 to 13) from *Fragaria vesca* strawberry. Insert B₁: MS² Scan spectra at
597 *m/z* 289 of (+)-catechin (peak 9), collision energy 20eV.

598 **Figure 2:** Extracted Ion Chromatogram (EIC) from HPLC-ESI-MS analysis
599 corresponding to procyanidin dimers B1 (peak 7) and B3 (peak 8). (Insert A): MS² Scan
600 spectra at *m/z* 577 of procyanidin dimer B1(EC-4,8-C) (peak 7). (Insert B): procyanidin
601 dimer B3(C-4,8-C) (peak 8). Collision energy 20eV. A fragment ion of *m/z* 289 was
602 found in the MS² spectra of these two procyanidins corresponding to a catechin
603 molecule.

604 **Figure 3:** Catechin content ($\mu\text{g/g}$ FW) in *Fragaria vesca* strawberries after harvesting
605 (pre-stored, 0 days) and after 3 days of storage at 0 °C in air (untreated), 20% CO₂ or
606 40% CO₂. The data are presented as the mean \pm SE of three replicates (n=6) and the
607 letters indicate significant differences ($p<0.05$).

608 **Figure 4:** Procyanidin B1 and Procyanidin B3 content $\mu\text{g/g}$ FW (expressed as catechin
609 equivalents) in *Fragaria vesca* strawberries after harvesting (pre-stored, 0 days) and
610 after 3 days of storage at 0 °C in air (untreated), 20% CO₂ or 40% CO₂. The data are
611 presented as the mean \pm SE of three replicates (n=6) and the letters indicate significant
612 differences ($p<0.05$).

Table 1: Characterization of flavonoids compounds in water extracts of *Fragaria vesca* cv. Mara de Bois strawberries by Mass Spectrometry detection in positive and negative mode. Rt (min), Retention time.

Peak	Rt (min)	MS IDENTIFICATION		MS ² IDENTIFICATION		
		Exact Mass Molecular ion [M ⁺]	Tentative Molecular Formula	Score %	MS ² (m/z) ^a	Tentative identification
1	8.4	433.1135	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₁₀ ⁺	95.88	271	Pelargonidin 3-O-glucoside
2	9.1	579.1714	C ₂₇ H ₃₁ O ₁₄ ⁺	98.13	271	Pelargonidin 3-O-rutinoside
3	11.4	535.1088	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ O ₁₄ ⁺	97.23	287	Cyanidin 3-O-(6"-malonyl)glucoside (1)
4	13.4	519.1139	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ O ₁₃ ⁺	95.71	271	Pelargonidin 3-O-(6"-malonyl-glucoside)
5	15.9	475.1240	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ O ₁₁ ⁺	99.17	271	Pelargonidin 3-O-(6"-acetyl)glucoside)
6	23.2	535.1088	C ₂₄ H ₂₃ O ₁₄ ⁺	92.17	287	Cyanidin 3-O-(6"-malonyl)glucoside (2)
Exact Mass Molecular ion [M-H]						
7	5.6	577.1351	C ₃₀ H ₂₆ O ₁₂	86.48	451, 407, 289 , 125	Procyanidin B1
8	6.8	577.1351	C ₃₀ H ₂₆ O ₁₂	89.80	451, 407, 289 , 125	Procyanidin B3
9	7.7	289.0718	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₆	92.26	245, 203, 179, 151, 109	(+)-Catechin
10	14.3	273.0768	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₅	84.76	255, 229, 187, 137 , 97	Afzelechin
11	17.5	477.0675	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₁₃	83.75	301	Quercetin 3-O-glucuronide
12	20.8	461.0725	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ O ₁₂	97.80	285 , 113, 59	Kaempferol 3-O-glucuronide
13	23.2	489.1038	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ O ₁₂	94.42	285	Kaempferol 3-O-acetyl-glucoside

^aThe most abundant ions are shown in bold. These ions are isolated for fragmentation in positive or negative mode.

Table 2: Anthocyanin contents in *Fragaria vesca* cv. Mara de Bois strawberries after harvesting (pre-stored, 0 days) and after 3 days of storage at 0 °C in air (untreated), 20% CO₂ or 40% CO₂. Data are expressed as µg pelargonidin equivalent per g FW.

	pre-stored	untreated	CO ₂ -treated	
	0d	3d air	3d 20% CO ₂	3d 40% CO ₂
Pelargonidin 3-O-glucoside	842.09±46.41 ^{ab}	973.45±42.24 ^c	917.58±12.70 ^{bc}	772.03±16.86 ^a
Pelargonidin 3-O-rutinoside	6.24±0.45 ^a	7.33±0.37 ^b	7.46±0.35 ^b	5.70±0.53 ^a
Cyanidin 3-O-(6"-malonyl)glucoside (1)	9.80±1.15 ^b	13.24±0.99 ^c	11.67±0.29 ^{bc}	6.44±0.45 ^a
Pelargonidin 3-O-(6"-malonyl-glucoside)	96.24±3.26 ^a	115.59±8.47 ^b	102.29±2.05 ^b	86.53±7.61 ^a
Pelargonidin 3-O-(6"-acetyl-glucoside)	7.59±0.67 ^a	6.43±0.48 ^a	7.18±0.47 ^a	9.49±0.63 ^b
Cyanidin 3-O-(6"-malonyl)glucoside (2)	0.82±0.18 ^b	0.83±0.16 ^b	1.17±0.01 ^b	0.40±0.07 ^a

The data are presented as the mean ± SE of three replicates (n=6) and the letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

Table 3: Flavonol contents in *Fragaria vesca* cv. Mara de Bois strawberries after harvesting (pre-stored, 0 days) and after 3 days of storage at 0 °C in air (untreated), 20% CO₂ or 40% CO₂. Data are expressed as µg catechin equivalent per g FW.

	pre-stored	untreated	CO ₂ -treated	
	0d	3d air	3d 20% CO ₂	3d 40% CO ₂
Quercetin 3-O-glucuronide	39.14±2.44 ^a	51.73±1.91 ^b	49.61±2.61 ^b	39.10±2.41 ^a
Kaempferol 3-O-glucuronide	3.99±0.21 ^a	4.98±0.20 ^b	5.16±0.34 ^b	3.81±0.21 ^a
Kaempferol 3-O-acetyl-glucoside	1.67±0.01 ^{ab}	1.81±0.08 ^{ab}	1.89±0.22 ^b	1.36±0.24 ^a

The data are presented as the mean ± SE of three replicates (n=6) and the letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

Table 4: Changes of the content of anthocyanins, flavonols, flavanols, ascorbic acid and antioxidant capacity of strawberry *Fragaria vesca* cv. Mara de Bois pre-stored, untreated and 20%CO₂ or 40%CO₂-treated stored for 3 days at 0 °C.

	pre-stored	untreated	CO ₂ -treated	
	0d	3d air	3d 20% CO ₂	3d 40% CO ₂
Sum of anthocyanins (mg/g FW)	0.96±0.34 ^{ab}	1.12±0.42 ^c	1.05±0.37 ^{bc}	0.88±0.31 ^a
Sum of flavonols (µg FW)	44.80±1.18 ^a	58.52±0.70 ^b	56.66±0.32 ^b	45.35±0.38 ^a
Sum of flavan-3-ols and dimers (µg FW)	26.39±1.40 ^b	11.03±0.78 ^a	38.52±0.34 ^c	35.01±0.41 ^c
Sum of Total flavonoids (mg/g FW)	1.03±8.82	1.18±8.09	1.14±2.37	0.962±3.19
Ascorbic acid (mg/g FW)	1.11±0.11 ^a	0.79±0.11 ^a	0.85±0.08 ^a	1.94±0.41 ^b
Antioxidant capacity (µg ascorbic acid equivalent /mg FW)	5.29±0.64 ^a	7.43±0.50 ^b	6.21±0.80 ^{ab}	6.60±0.61 ^{ab}

The different letters indicate significant differences at $p < 0.05$

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

TOC graphic

Simplified schematic of the flavanols, anthocyanins and proanthocyanidins production, account for the major products found in *Fragaria vesca* strawberries as proposed to be regulated by high CO₂ atmospheres.